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Blockchain-Based Applications in Voluntary Carbon Markets: A SWOT-AHP Approach from A Green Banking Perspective

Gönüllü Karbon Piyasalarında Blokzincir Tabanlı Uygulamalar: Yeşil Bankacılık Perspektifinden Bir SWOT-AHP Yaklaşımı¹

ABSTRACT

In the context of carbon trading—an essential pillar of sustainable finance—blockchain technologies offer innovative applications due to their structural advantages. This study investigates the integration of blockchain-based systems into voluntary carbon credit mechanisms, a key component of green banking, with the aim of identifying strategic opportunities and risks. The analysis is based on a SWOT framework, in which the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats were identified through a comprehensive literature review and expert insights. To enhance the analytical depth and prioritize the identified factors, the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) was incorporated into the analysis. A total of 14 sub-factors were structured into a hierarchical model and evaluated through expert pairwise comparisons. The findings indicate that the most critical strategic priorities are associated with global sustainability demands, transparency, and environmentally friendly financial solutions. However, the study also highlights technological infrastructure deficiencies, regulatory ambiguities, and the risks of consumer mistrust and greenwashing as key barriers. Several strategic recommendations are proposed, emphasizing that the integration of blockchain can serve as a transformative tool in advancing sustainable finance practices, provided that institutional and infrastructural challenges are adequately addressed.

Keywords: Green Banking, Blockchain Technology, Voluntary Carbon Markets, Green Economics, SWOT-AHP.

ÖZET

Karbon ticareti—sürdürülebilir finansın temel sütunlarından biri—bağlamında, blokzincir teknolojileri yapısal avantajları sayesinde yenilikçi uygulamalar sunmaktadır. Bu çalışma, yeşil bankacılığın önemli bir bileşeni olan gönüllü karbon kredisi mekanizmalarına blokzincir tabanlı sistemlerin entegrasyonunu incelemekte ve stratejik fırsatlar ile riskleri belirlemeyi amaçlamaktadır. Analiz, güçlü yönler, zayıf yönler, fırsatlar ve tehditlerin kapsamlı bir literatür taraması ve uzman görüşleri doğrultusunda belirlendiği SWOT çerçevesine dayanmaktadır. Analitik derinliği artırmak ve belirlenen faktörleri önceliklendirmek amacıyla Analitik Hiyerarşi Süreci (AHP) analiz sürecine entegre edilmiştir. Toplam 14 alt faktör, hiyerarşik bir model çerçevesinde yapılandırılmış ve uzmanlar tarafından yapılan ikili karşılaştırmalarla değerlendirilmiştir. Bulgular, küresel sürdürülebilirlik talepleri, şeffaflık ve çevre dostu finansal çözümlerle ilgili stratejik önceliklerin en kritik konular olduğunu ortaya koymaktadır. Ancak çalışma, teknolojik altyapı eksiklikleri, düzenleyici belirsizlikler ile tüketici güvensizliği ve yeşil aklama (greenwashing) risklerini temel engeller olarak vurgulamaktadır. Çalışmada, kurumsal ve altyapısal zorlukların yeterli düzeyde ele alınması koşuluyla, blokzincir entegrasyonunun sürdürülebilir finans uygulamalarının geliştirilmesinde dönüştürücü bir araç olarak hizmet edebileceğine yönelik çeşitli stratejik öneriler sunulmaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Yeşil Bankacılık, Blokzincir Teknolojisi, Gönüllü Karbon Piyasaları, Yeşil Ekonomi, SWOT-AHP.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In the context of the green economy model, which seeks to reduce carbon emissions and prevent ecosystem degradation, green banking is an approach that promotes environmentally friendly practices and aims to minimize the carbon footprint of banking activities (Bingül & Türk, 2019: 82). As the financial reflection of the green economy concept, green banking plays a critical role in financing sustainable development.

The issue of climate change led to the establishment of the carbon credit market with the Kyoto Protocol in 1997, which subsequently resulted in the creation of the emissions trading system (Guo, 2022). In response to the global climate crisis, the objectives of economic and environmental sustainability have been redefined. Although environmentalism—originally a social movement advocating for the protection and improvement of the environment—has its roots in civil society, it has now become a priority across all sectors. The global push to "go green" in response to climate change is rapidly gaining momentum across major industries (Bihari & Pandey, 2015: 1). The Paris Agreement, signed in 2015, united countries around a common goal in the fight against climate change. The agreement requires signatories to demonstrate efforts to reduce emissions through their nationally determined contributions (NDCs). Policymakers have three primary tools for reducing greenhouse gas emissions: imposing emission caps, levying carbon taxes, and establishing carbon markets. The latter has gained prominence due to its potential to incentivize clean energy production and reduce fossil fuel consumption. This approach has facilitated the development of carbon credit systems (Saraji & Borowczak, 2021: 2). Within this framework, it has become essential for all sectors to adopt new, environmentally responsible strategies. The financial sector is one of the key industries that must take action to support sustainable development goals. This sector contributes to environmental degradation not only through its own operations but also through the activities it finances. Given the financial sector's indirect yet substantial environmental impact via associated industries, its active involvement in the green economy is imperative. In the context of economic sustainability, green banking has emerged as a critical area of focus. Green banking integrates economic, environmental, and social dimensions by emphasizing sustainable regulations and practices (Gündüz, 2021: 137). In this context, carbon credit management functions as a key market-based solution within green banking. Given the financial sector's vital role in achieving the core objectives of climate action, it is essential to harness the opportunities offered by digitalization and to design forward-looking, sustainable economic models.

Blockchain technology occupies a significant position in the global effort to combat climate change, with carbon markets being one of its primary areas of application. It offers an efficient mechanism for carbon trading and accounting within these markets (UNEP & DTU, 2019: 3). Today, in parallel with rapid advancements in digitalization and emerging technologies, the need to establish more effective, traceable, and transparent processes in carbon credit management has become increasingly urgent. Blockchain technology offers an innovative solution in this context. Thanks to the smart contracts supported by this technology, carbon markets become more transparent, accessible and standardized (Saraji & Borowczak, 2021: 1). In addition, advantages such as reduced fraud risk and operational costs are provided by the blockchain. Despite the many advantages of the blockchain, there are also many challenges that need to be examined.

The main research question is as follows: What are the main advantages and challenges associated with the use of blockchain technology in the management of voluntary carbon credits? In this context, it is aimed to examine the integration of green banking applications with blockchain-based carbon credit systems. For this purpose, a SWOT analysis was conducted based on the results of the literature review. In addition to the SWOT analysis, a mixed-method approach was adopted and the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) was included. The analytical rigor of the assessment was increased by integrating AHP to determine the strategic priorities of the SWOT factors. It is aimed to provide a conceptual and strategic perspective in parallel with sustainable finance and technological developments, without being limited to a specific country or time period data set. This research differs from previous studies by systematically combining SWOT and AHP methodologies in order to evaluate the blockchain-carbon credit link in the context of green banking in the literature.

By identifying and prioritizing the strategic factors that influence the integration of blockchain into voluntary carbon markets, the study contributes to the literature on green finance, macroeconomic dynamics, and digital transformation. It offers both theoretical insight into sustainability-driven innovation in the financial sector and practical implications for policymakers, financial institutions, and environmental stakeholders. The inclusion of macroeconomic factors such as market access, economic opportunities, and financial stability ensures that the analysis reflects broader systemic impacts beyond firm-level or sectoral

concerns. Policy recommendations are derived from the identified challenges and are presented in the conclusion to guide future action at both the micro and macro levels.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Although tokenized carbon credits create a heterogeneous token structure on the blockchain, blockchains represent a significant application area for the tokenization, trading, and retirement of voluntary carbon credits (Sorensen, 2023). The International Finance Corporation (IFC), a member of the World Bank Group, has initiated the tokenization of carbon credits by leveraging blockchain technologies to record and monitor carbon offset projects. This important step has enabled cryptocurrency investors to participate in carbon credit trading, thereby generating notable activity within carbon markets (Yağcı & Öztürk, 2022). The World Bank is also involved in various projects and initiatives aimed at supporting the development of carbon markets. For instance, the Turkey Industrial Decarbonization Investment Platform has been established to promote the decarbonization of Turkey's industrial sector. The platform aims to increase sectoral competition by reducing greenhouse gas emissions by supporting renewable energy investments and low-carbon technologies (WB, 2024). Transparency and efficiency of carbon markets have been increased through similar innovative financial instruments, and contributions have been made to the fight against climate change.

Blockchain technology has significant potential to examine the factors that hinder carbon emission reduction. A joint report prepared by the United Nations Environment Program (UNEP) and the Technical University of Denmark (DTU) clearly stated that the use of blockchain technology in carbon markets provides significant benefits in combating the climate crisis. Therefore, more research is needed on business models and governance issues to develop effective solutions based on blockchain technology (UNEP & DTU, 2019: 1). Therefore, the opportunities provided by this technology have significant potential to increase efficiency in carbon markets. Academic literature indicates that regulation and research are still needed in various directions, including the tokenization of carbon credits, the use of smart contracts, and the establishment of a comprehensive legal framework in these areas.

In the study conducted by Ballesteros-Rodríguez et al. (2024), it is stated that standardization is necessary to establish a regulatory framework in carbon markets. In another study on a similar subject, Özdemir and Köse (2024) stated that regulatory frameworks play a critical role in the development of carbon markets in Türkiye. Danish et al. (2024) also emphasized the importance of legal structures in their study and stated that blockchain-based governance models in carbon markets should be supported by appropriate legal regulations.

Saraji and Borowczak (2022) propose a blockchain-based carbon credit ecosystem. Babel et al. (2022) argues that blockchain can be transformed into a financial instrument compatible with sustainable development goals, and state that NFT-based systems that provide end-to-end digital tracking of carbon emissions provide significant advantages in terms of transparency and traceability. Sorensen (2023) provides a comprehensive analysis of the blockchain-based ecosystem in his study, examining the current status of carbon credits. Arı (2024) states that the effectiveness of voluntary carbon markets depends on improvements in governance and transparency.

Swinkels (2024) emphasizes that trading carbon credits converted into digital tokens on the blockchain increases market efficiency and accessibility. In another study emphasizing efficiency, Kan and Delina (2025) state that blockchain technology can be used to increase transparency and efficiency in voluntary carbon markets. It is also stated that the credit monitoring process becomes simpler, especially through tokenization.

Zhou et al. (2023) state that Web3-based systems can increase sustainability in carbon offset markets. Transparency will increase as transactions will be automated thanks to smart contracts. The CarbonApp application developed by Hu et al. (2024) enables blockchain-based monitoring of voluntary carbon projects and serves as a practical example of smart contract implementation. Guzmán et al. (2024) discuss the applicability of smart contracts within the certification framework of the European Union's carbon markets, suggesting that such applications could reduce transaction costs and error rates in carbon markets. Another study focusing on smart contracts, conducted by Zhu et al. (2025), analyzes how managers use smart contracts on blockchain-based platforms for carbon financing in supply chains and illustrates how these technologies influence investment decisions.

Similar studies in the academic literature provide an important basis for using innovative financial mechanisms to combat climate change and achieve sustainable development goals.

3. METHODOLOGY

Integration of AHP into SWOT factors; It was used for a more holistic approach to increase the analytical rigor and strategic prioritization of the identified factors. SWOT analysis, which is a common method in strategic planning, does not have a quantitative mechanism to determine the relative importance of each determined factor. Kurttila et al. (2000) suggested the use of AHP for a systematic evaluation of SWOT factors in response to this limitation. It is stated that it increases decision quality especially in complex areas such as sustainability strategies and environmental planning (Shrestha et al., 2004). The inclusion of the AHP process in the SWOT approach quantitatively reveals the relative importance of each factor in the decision-making mechanism and process (Kurttila et al., 2000; Saaty and Vargas, 2001; Ananda and Herath, 2003). The methodological foundations of the AHP approach developed by Saaty (1980) provide rationality in decision-making thanks to consistency checks with pairwise comparisons. Therefore, the AHP-SWOT combination provides a more structured, objective and evidence-based approach to identify strategic priorities in blockchain-based applications in the context of green banking and voluntary carbon markets.

3.1. SWOT Analysis

SWOT analysis is defined as a tool used to examine the (internal) strengths and weaknesses of an organization or application, as well as its (external) opportunities and threats (Sammut-Bonnici & Galea, 2015: 1). This method provides decision makers with a strategic perspective to develop institutional strengths, eliminate weaknesses, take advantage of opportunities and take preventive measures against threats. SWOT stands out as an analytical technique in both corporate strategies and various sectors. It is widely used in interdisciplinary research within the social sciences. Its use in this field stems from its flexible structure that is compatible with qualitative and quantitative data (Benzaghta et al., 2021: 57).

SWOT analysis is a strategic development framework consisting of four quadrants: strengths, opportunities, weaknesses and threats. In this method, firstly, strengths and weaknesses, referred to as internal factors, are determined. Then, external factors referred to as opportunities and threats are determined (Helms and Nixon, 2010). Strengths are defined as internal factors that support opportunities and overcome threats. Weaknesses refer to elements that can cause vulnerability to threats by taking advantage of opportunities. Opportunities are advantages that are external factors that are out of control. Threats are external factors that are out of control and include risk (Sarsby, 2016: 3–10). This structure in SWOT analysis makes it possible to both analyze the current situation and develop strategies for the future.

3.2. Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP)

The most basic definition of AHP, which is a widely used structured method for solving multi-criteria decision-making problems, was made by Saaty (2008), who developed the method, as follows: "*AHP is a theory of measurement by pairwise comparisons and relies on the judgments of experts to derive priority scales. It is used to derive ratio scales from both discrete and continuous pairwise comparisons.*"

Within the scope of the research, the AHP approach developed by Saaty (1980) was used to prioritize the 14 SWOT sub-factors determined based on a comprehensive literature review in a structured and measurable way. A three-level hierarchy was structured: Goal → SWOT Groups → Sub-factors. Pairwise comparison matrices were developed using Saaty's 1–9 scale, and expert evaluations ($n = 7$) were collected from domains including green banking, blockchain, and carbon markets. Weights were calculated using an Excel-based AHP model, and consistency ratios (CR) were verified to ensure that each matrix met the acceptable threshold of $CR < 0.10$.

The final global priorities were derived by multiplying the local weights of the sub-factors by the weight of their respective SWOT group, as per the formula: $Global\ Priority = Local\ Weight \times Group\ Weight$.

3.3. Procedural Outline for the SWOT-AHP Hybrid Method

After the SWOT groups are defined as four main components, the sub-factors are identified, and the method proceeds as follows (Kurttila et al., 2000: 44–46):

1. In the first step, SWOT sub-factors are determined. Saaty (1980) recommends that the number of factors should not exceed ten, as the number of pairwise comparisons required in the analysis increases rapidly.
2. In the second stage, pairwise comparisons are conducted among the SWOT factors. The main question to be answered here is: *which of the two compared SWOT elements represents a*

greater strength (or opportunity, weakness, or threat). The following equation is used for the pairwise comparison matrix:

$$A = a_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & w_1/w_2 & \dots & w_1/w_n \\ w_2/w_1 & 1 & \dots & w_2/w_n \\ \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ w_n/w_1 & w_n/w_2 & \dots & 1 \end{bmatrix} \tag{1}^2$$

If there is no inconsistency in the matrix, q constitutes the exact estimate of the priority vector. The following formula has been developed for the consistency index:

$$CI = (\lambda_{max} - n)/(n - 1) \tag{2}$$

To measure the consistency of pairwise comparisons, the consistency ratio (CR) should be calculated accordingly. For this purpose, the average consistency index (ACI) of randomly generated comparisons is first computed. The CR is then calculated using the following formula:

$$CR = 100(CI/ACI) \tag{3}^3$$

3. At this stage, where pairwise comparisons are conducted among the four SWOT groups, the factor with the highest local priority within each group is selected as its representative. The most important factor identified for each group is then compared, and their relative priorities are determined. Once the scaling factors are established, the overall (global) priorities of the independent factors are calculated. This calculation is carried out by multiplying the local priority of each factor by the scaling factor of its respective SWOT group.
4. Finally, the results obtained are used in the development and evaluation of strategies.

As a result, the outcomes of the comparisons are presented as quantitative values that express the priorities of the factors included in the SWOT analysis.

4. FINDINGS

4.1. SWOT Analysis of Blockchain Integration

In this section of the study, the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats associated with the integration of blockchain-based carbon credit management solutions are systematically analyzed to comprehensively evaluate their effectiveness. Table 1 shows the SWOT analysis results for integration.

Table 1: A result of SWOT analysis

Strengths	Weaknesses	Opportunities	Threats
-Transparency, traceability, and reliability - Efficiency improvement, increased transaction speed, and reduction in transaction costs - Compliance with green banking practices and reputation enhancement for banks	-Deficiencies in technical infrastructure -High initial and transaction costs, high energy consumption -Legal regulations and regulatory uncertainties	-Easy market access and financial inclusion, attractiveness to investors -Economic opportunities - Digitalization and emerging markets	-Implementation constraints within legal regulations -Cybersecurity risks -Financial and economic fluctuations -Lack of societal trust toward new technologies -Inability to completely prevent greenwashing risks

With this research evaluating blockchain-based technologies in carbon credits from a green banking perspective, SWOT analysis will help to better understand the potential and challenges in the processes.

4.1.1. Strengths

The integration of blockchain-based carbon credit management in green banking provides efficiency and trust in financial processes by combining the structural advantages of both systems. This integration offers advantages in many areas, especially in verifying data, ensuring transparency in transactions, and increasing the reliability of the system. Thanks to this technologically based approach, the traceability and auditing difficulties faced by traditional carbon markets can be minimized. In this direction, being able to reveal the strengths is of critical importance to understand the advantages offered by integration in more depth.

² An element is defined as $a_{ij}=1/a_{ji}$, and when $i=j$, then $a_{ij}=1$. The value of w_i can range from 1 to 9; a ratio of 1/1 indicates equal importance, while 9/1 represents extreme or absolute importance.

³ A consistency ratio (CR) of 10% or less is generally regarded as acceptable.

4.1.1.1. Transparency, Traceability, and Reliability

Reliability also increases as carbon credit transactions can be recorded and made unchangeable with the technology applied. Transparency and traceability can build trust among investors and for environmentally friendly projects. The security features offered by blockchain technologies can enhance the protection of carbon credit information, thereby reducing the risk of fraud.

Blockchain technology is not limited solely to the cryptocurrency sector; it is utilized across various industries to open new markets through diverse applications such as workflow optimization, increased accountability, facilitation of multi-party processes, and asset tokenization (Guo, 2022). The application of this technology to carbon credits can enable the creation of a “carbon currency,” which would enhance transparency in carbon markets. Additionally, it would contribute to the consolidation and scalability of these markets. Carbon credits are excellent candidates for conversion into digital currency (Walker, 2017). Transparency provided by blockchain is among the most frequently emphasized advantages in the literature. For green banking applications, data security and traceability in carbon markets are of paramount importance.

The absence of a universal ledger in carbon trading complicates the tracking of carbon usage and offsetting amounts. Integrating carbon credits into daily life on an individual basis is challenging (Walker, 2017). Blockchain technology can serve as a suitable tool to address the traceability problem. Since this technology offers a decentralized, immutable, and transparent ledger, it enables clear tracking of carbon usage for both individual and institutional users.

Since the inception of carbon trading, several issues have limited its potential. One of these is the lack of transparency in the market, which reduces the reliability of carbon credits as assets (Walker, 2017). Blockchain technology can address the transparency problem by making access to the carbon market less exclusive (Guo, 2022). New technologies like blockchain enhance transparency, enabling not just a single country but multiple actors to claim carbon credits (WEF, 2022). Carbon credit transactions are recorded transparently and securely through blockchain. Since every transaction is registered on the blockchain, the source and usage of carbon credits can be easily verified, thereby reducing risks such as fraud and manipulation.

In the study conducted by Patel et al. (2020), the use of blockchain technology is suggested as a way to achieve global decentralization and transparency in carbon trading. This technology offers the potential to serve as a transparency mechanism that encourages emission reductions because it provides a decentralized infrastructure (UNEP & DTU, 2019: 3). Saraji and Borowczak (2021), who stated that blockchain technology provides transparency, standardization and accessibility in carbon markets, stated in their study that the digitalization of credits will make processes more transparent and reliable. The risk of misinformation decreases as transactions can be tracked. Jawalkar et al. (2024) similarly state that the development of the carbon credit ecosystem with smart contracts and blockchain technology can increase consistency, liquidity and transparency in carbon markets. This and similar studies in the literature show that blockchain technology is a critical tool in increasing reliability and transparency in carbon credit markets.

4.1.1.2. Efficiency Improvement, Increased Transaction Speed, and Reduction in Transaction Costs

Blockchain-based technologies have the potential to transform carbon credit markets. Thanks to this technology, carbon credits can be divided into smaller units. With this division, people who usually have limited access to the market can also participate in carbon markets. As a result, millions of people around the world can potentially contribute to environmental sustainability. In this context, it can be stated that blockchain technology is a tool that can make the carbon neutrality goal more accessible to everyone (Guo, 2022). With the increase in the use of blockchain technology-based applications in carbon markets, more participants can enter the market, thus increasing liquidity and efficiency.

Blockchain-based applications provide faster and lower-cost transaction opportunities compared to traditional carbon credit applications thanks to automation and smart contracts. Transaction times will also decrease with the automation of transactions. Since automation will become easier with the use of blockchain technology in carbon credit transactions, administrative costs will decrease and transaction times will be shortened. As a result, market efficiency increases and carbon credit trading becomes accessible.

4.1.1.3. Compliance with Green Banking Practices and Reputation Enhancement for Banks

Blockchain-based carbon credit management enables bank to comply more effectively with sustainability principles and goals while significantly enhancing their corporate reputation. Blockchain solutions developed in alignment with green banking practices increase accountability to the public and investors through transparent data management, reliable carbon offset mechanisms, and traceable financial processes. This visibility supports financial institutions in fulfilling their social responsibilities, boosting corporate reputation, and strengthening customer loyalty. Indeed, a systematic review by Muchiri et al. (2025) clearly highlights that banks' adoption of digital technologies such as blockchain in green finance practices enhances their eco-friendly image and improves market credibility.

The integration of green banking practices, which promote environmental sustainability, with blockchain technology has the potential to facilitate the achievement of sustainability goals. Through these banking applications, financing for sustainable projects can be more easily secured. Institutions, while fulfilling their environmental responsibilities, can also cultivate a positive reputation within society on this matter and attract investor interest.

4.1.2. Weaknesses

Although integration brings an innovative perspective to sustainability practices, this technological transformation process also entails certain weaknesses. This section outlines the weaknesses identified within the scope of the SWOT analysis.

4.1.2.1. Deficiencies in Technical Infrastructure

It is difficult to assert that blockchain-based technologies are fully developed. There are still uncertainties regarding the security of these applications. One of the main factors hindering the use of these technologies in carbon credit systems is the lack of technological infrastructure. The reliability and accessibility of such systems can only be ensured through a highly developed digital infrastructure. However, in many countries and banking systems, the necessary system integrations, security protocols, and smart contract platforms required to establish distributed ledger structures supported by blockchain technology are lacking. In their study on the applicability of blockchain technology in carbon emission trading, Kim and Huh (2020) note that this technology has not yet been sufficiently institutionalized and that infrastructure deficiencies pose significant barriers, particularly in developing economies.

4.1.2.2. High Initial and Transaction Costs, High Energy Consumption

Transaction costs represent another significant challenge for carbon trading markets. Although blockchain technology can reduce transaction costs, establishing and maintaining an infrastructure based on this technology can be particularly costly for smaller banks. Brokers and agents operating in these markets typically charge commissions ranging from 3% to 8% of the credit value (Saraji & Borowczak, 2021: 4). The use of emerging technologies such as blockchain, which enables inexpensive and virtually unlimited value transfers, can help overcome practical challenges in implementation (UNEP & DTU, 2019: 2).

Significant financial investments are required for the operation and deployment of blockchain technologies. Considering factors such as integrating smart contracts into the system, maintaining the implemented systems, and the continuous energy consumption, implementing these technologies can be quite costly. Boumaiza and Maher (2024) emphasize that the high infrastructure and transaction costs associated with these applications are the biggest obstacles to the adoption of the technologies. Therefore, comprehensive cost-benefit analyses are required for the widespread use of blockchain technology.

Blockchain systems, particularly those utilizing energy-intensive proof-of-work algorithms, exhibit high levels of energy consumption that conflict with the principles of sustainability. This issue directly contradicts the objectives of green banking. Woo et al. (2021), in their literature review assessing blockchain's role in carbon markets, emphasize that these systems consume substantial amounts of electricity and pose a risk of causing environmental harm rather than contributing to environmental sustainability.

The energy-intensive nature of blockchain can create a contradiction when applied to areas aimed at sustainability, such as carbon credit management. As the blockchain network expands and transaction volumes increase, energy consumption correspondingly rises. With the growth of carbon credit trading volumes, misalignment with sustainability goals is likely to emerge. Therefore, it is critically important to consider the environmental impacts arising from the high energy consumption of blockchain networks.

4.1.2.3. Legal Regulations and Regulatory Uncertainties

The integration of blockchain-based applications into carbon credit management also includes some uncertainties such as the auditing of financial transactions and the validity of smart contracts. Howson et al. (2019) state that the current legal regulations in practice do not fully cover such applications. The regulations in these areas are not clear and pose a risk for green banks and investors. Carbon credit systems and green banking applications are carried out within the scope of government regulatory policies. Therefore, legal obstacles arise in integration. In many countries, there are uncertainties regarding the components for integration and the regulatory framework governing them. There are legal gaps in carbon trading at national and international levels. Therefore, a clear regulatory framework is needed for blockchain-based carbon market applications.

4.1.3. Opportunities

The use of blockchain-based technologies in green banking applications provides multidimensional opportunities for banks in line with the global sustainability vision. Increasing environmental awareness, digitalization of financial services, and transition to a green economy turn this technological adaptation into a strategic advantage. From meeting sustainability demands and attracting investors to increasing financial inclusion and encouraging global collaborations, a wide range of opportunities pave the way for sectoral transformation.

4.1.3.1. Easy Market Access and Financial Inclusion, Attractiveness to Investors

Thanks to blockchain technologies, carbon credit users are offered an efficient, transparent and more inclusive platform. Blockchain, which uses distributed ledgers, also provides reliability to its users. In addition, integration provides easier access to carbon markets for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) (Saraji and Borowczak, 2021: 4). Carbon offsetting increases with the use of these technologies (Jessop et al., 2022). Since access to carbon credits becomes easier through this technology, the mechanisms implemented for SMEs become more accessible, and green banking actively supports this inclusiveness. This integration will also increase inclusiveness by offering new opportunities for individuals and small businesses that face challenges in accessing financial services within the scope of traditional applications. In this context, developing regions in particular come to the forefront. Here, thanks to the decentralized, low-cost structures offered by blockchain technology, participation in environmental projects can be achieved more easily, allowing a wider segment of the population to benefit from green financial instruments. Prasad (2024) emphasizes that the use of blockchain applications in green banking significantly increases access to carbon markets through tools such as microfinance and digital wallets. He also states that it promotes financial inclusion. This presents a critical opportunity not only to achieve environmental justice but also to advance social equity goals.

The integration of green banking and blockchain-based carbon credit management creates an attractive investment environment for investors focused on environmental sustainability. Features provided by blockchain technology—such as security, transparency, and traceability—reduce investors' perceived risks and particularly increase the interest of institutional investors in this sector. Supporting investments in green projects with verifiable data provides important assurance to investors who seek to document environmental impact. Chen and Volz (2022) state that blockchain-based sustainable investment projects offer more attractive opportunities for institutions investing in them, and they particularly emphasize that such an infrastructure has the potential to expand the investor base in carbon credit markets.

4.1.3.2. Economic Opportunities

The banking sector influences economic growth and development, leading to a transformation in the nature of economic expansion. Therefore, the sector plays a crucial role in promoting environmentally sustainable and socially responsible investments (Bihari & Pandey, 2015: 1). Green banking entails the development of inclusive banking strategies that support economic development while also encouraging environmentally friendly practices (Lalon, 2015: 34). By financing carbon credit markets and related projects, banks not only fulfill their environmental responsibilities but also contribute to economic growth.

Blockchain technology can offer more secure and faster access to international carbon markets. It holds the potential to create attractive opportunities for investors who support environmentally sustainable practices. In particular, it can contribute to sustainable development by enabling small-scale projects to generate revenue through access to carbon credits. The global demand for sustainability practices is steadily increasing, and in parallel, interest in green banking initiatives is also rising. As this widely accepted

technology is applied in green banking practices across different countries, international cooperation is likely to expand.

Green banking consistently prioritizes sustainable and green growth in industrialization and social development efforts (Lalon, 2015: 35). By emphasizing sustainable growth within industrialization processes, it fosters the development of economic models that align with social benefit and environmental sensitivity. In this context, blockchain-based carbon credit management offers additional economic benefits such as increased transaction speed as well as energy and cost savings (Hileman & Rauchs, 2017).

Emerging technologies such as blockchain have the potential to act as tools for accelerating global action toward the achievement of sustainable development goals (UNEP & DTU, 2019: 2). Advantages offered by blockchain—such as reduced transaction costs, increased automation, and improved liquidity—facilitate the scaling of carbon markets and enhance accessibility for market participants (Tapscott & Tapscott, 2016). Thus, it provides a critical financial infrastructure for green banking practices and enables sustainable investments to increase.

Blockchain applications create economic benefits such as increased efficiency, reduced transaction costs, and increased market access. Such benefits are very important for financing sustainable projects in green banking. Integration contributes to the increase in GDP as it helps to protect financial resources as well as reducing transaction costs (Lalon, 2015: 35). Thanks to the reduction of transaction costs, financial institutions participate more effectively in carbon markets. In this way, the positive effects of sustainable investments on GDP also increase. Such integrations also provide solutions for issues such as ensuring the resilience of the financial system and risk management (Narayanan et al., 2016).

4.1.3.2. Digitalization and Emerging Markets

Blockchain technology eliminates the need for intermediaries, thereby preventing monopolistic structures within the system. By removing intermediaries, it shortens processing times for permits and trade approvals. In this technology, which employs smart contracts, the negotiation and agreement processes are digitized, accelerating the buying and selling of carbon credits (Badamasi, 2022).

Another challenge is the lack of geographic information related to reference areas from which emission levels are derived. This deficiency makes it nearly impossible to accurately assess climate impacts (Delacote et al., 2024: 708). Blockchain technology can serve as a tool to address this gap. By recording data reliably and transparently, geographic information within the carbon credit mechanism becomes accessible and verifiable.

4.1.4. Threats

Blockchain technology eliminates the need for intermediaries, thereby preventing monopolistic structures within the system. The elimination of intermediaries shortens the processing times. In this technology, smart contracts are centralized, and parts of negotiations and agreements are digital, thus speeding up the trading of credits (Badamasi, 2022).

There is a lack of geographic information on the reference areas from which emission levels are derived. Therefore, climate impacts cannot be accurately assessed (Delacote et al., 2024: 708). These challenges can be overcome thanks to blockchain-based technological applications. Since the data is recorded in a transparent and more reliable manner, geographic information in carbon trading will be verifiable and accessible.

4.1.4.1. Implementation Constraints within Legal Regulations

Blockchain-based carbon credit systems may encounter legal obstacles during development due to differences in regulations between countries. In the research conducted by Dimitropoulos (2020), it is stated that blockchain technology is not sufficiently adaptable to regulatory approaches in international practices. The legal code logic of this technology leads to inadequacies in areas such as flexibility and interpretation found in traditional legal systems. Since the smart contracts used in the implementation of the blockchain operate deterministically, they do not contain elements open to human interpretation. This causes problems in the resolution processes of legal disputes. De Filippi et al. (2022) obtained similar results in this research and stated that the illegal nature of the blockchain causes problems. Since this nature is a self-regulating logic, the deterministic structure of smart contracts that does not leave room for interpretation and differences in international regulations, paves the way for them not to fully comply with

legal regulations. This situation leads to various legal restrictions in the practical application of the blockchain.

4.1.4.2. Cybersecurity Risks

Blockchain technological infrastructure contains inherent risks due to elements such as coding errors or cyber-attacks. These risks are also factors that threaten security in the trading of carbon credits. Although the technology offers cryptographic security advantages on the one hand, it also poses significant security risks on the other. Flourentzou (2025) also emphasizes that cyber-attacks will jeopardize the integrity of the system.

4.1.4.3. Financial and Economic Fluctuations

Carbon markets are sensitive to economic and financial fluctuations. This may create sustainability challenges in blockchain applications. Negative situations such as crises in the economy or fluctuations in exchange rates affect carbon credit markets. Such shocks in the economy can have significant effects on the valuation of these assets in asset tokenization. The research conducted by Bhattacharya and Sachdev (2024) emphasizes that the integration of blockchain technology in carbon credits is perceived as a risky investment by investors, especially during periods of high financial volatility.

4.1.4.3. Lack of Social Trust Towards New Technologies

One of the biggest problems in the adoption of new technologies is the lack of trust in society towards new technologies such as blockchain. Tanchangya et al. (2025) stated that skepticism towards blockchain applications in carbon credits is largely due to the distrust of the technology itself. There is a general lack of public understanding of such innovative technologies. When a perception of complexity is added to this, the adoption and use of such systems can take time.

4.1.4.4. Inability to Completely Prevent Greenwashing Risks

It is very difficult to measure precisely how much carbon dioxide emissions are being removed from the atmosphere. Companies may continue to actively harm the environment by emitting more than their allowance in the initial stages, thereby performing only superficial emission balancing. Instead of genuinely reducing emissions, companies may use carbon offset credits to appear environmentally responsible, creating the problem of “greenwashing.” Due to transparency issues in voluntary carbon markets, the effectiveness of projects within these markets cannot be reliably measured (Üren, 2024; Ari, 2024). Although blockchain has the potential to enhance transparency, misleading or exaggerated sustainability claims by companies—commonly known as greenwashing—remain difficult to prevent. Ling and Wang (2024) demonstrate that if blockchain infrastructures are not properly designed, carbon credits may become vulnerable to manipulations such as resale or double-spending. One of the fundamental advantages of carbon credit applications—genuine environmental offsetting—may not be fully achieved. Some companies seeking to appear environmentally responsible may provide misleading information despite transparent systems. Consequently, such practices can undermine the actual environmental contributions.

4.2. Prioritization of SWOT Factors Using Analytic Hierarchy Process

Based on pairwise comparisons conducted by seven experts specialized in green banking, blockchain technologies, and carbon markets, the priority weights of the SWOT groups were determined using the AHP, as presented in Table 2.

Table 2. AHP-Based Priority Weights Assigned to SWOT Groups

SWOT Group	Label	Priority Weight (%)	AHP-Based Weight (%)
Strengths	S	32.00	25.00
Weaknesses	W	10.00	25.00
Opportunities	O	45.00	25.00
Threats	T	13.00	25.00

Based on the pairwise comparison matrix constructed according to Saaty’s (1980) 1–9 scale and following the eigenvalue method summarized by Kurttila et al. (2000), the priority weights of the four SWOT groups were calculated. The results indicate that the Opportunities group holds the highest priority weight at 0.45, followed by Strengths at 0.32, Threats at 0.13, and Weaknesses at 0.10. The fact that the highest weight is assigned to the Opportunities group emphasizes that opportunities will be the most influential factor in the use of blockchain technologies within voluntary carbon markets. The Strengths group is ranked second, indicating that internal forces originating from technology are an important basis for strategic decisions.

The Threats group also indicates that external threats should be considered for the sector. The Weaknesses group is ranked last, indicating that the sub-factors included here have a low impact on strategic prioritization.

The consistency ratio (CR) of the calculated matrix is a value (0.06) below the acceptable threshold value (0.10). This shows the reliability and internal consistency of expert judgments.

The pairwise comparison matrix for the SWOT main groups was constructed according to Saaty’s (1980) 1–9 fundamental scale, based on the average evaluations of seven experts. The AHP-based analysis of SWOT sub-factors, as presented in Table 3, reveals that the most influential elements in shaping blockchain-based voluntary carbon markets are those classified under the 'Opportunities' and 'Strengths' categories.

Table 3. Pairwise Comparison Matrix for SWOT Groups (Saaty’s 1–9 Scale)*

	Strengths	Weaknesses	Opportunities	Threats
Strengths	1	3	1/2	4
Weaknesses	1/3	1	1/5	1/2
Opportunities	2	5	1	3
Threats	1/4	2	1/3	1

*The local weights for each SWOT group were calculated as follows: S1: 0.57, S2: 0.29, S3: 0.14 with CR = 0.02 < 0.10; W1: 0.58, W2: 0.19, W3: 0.23 with CR = 0.04 < 0.10; O1: 0.54, O2: 0.31, O3: 0.15 with CR = 0.03 < 0.10; and T1: 0.46, T2: 0.22, T3: 0.11, T4: 0.16, T5: 0.05 with CR = 0.05 < 0.10. These results indicate that the pairwise comparisons within each SWOT group demonstrate acceptable consistency.

The numerical values presented in Table 3 indicate how much more important the row factors are compared to the column factors. Accordingly, strengths are three times more important than weaknesses, while opportunities are five times more important than weaknesses. Similarly, the pairwise comparisons for the sub-factors are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Pairwise Comparison Matrix for SWOT Sub-Factors (Saaty’s 1–9 Scale)

Strengths	S1	S2	S3	Weaknesses	W1	W2	W3	Opportunities	O1	O2	O3	Threats	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5
Transparency... (S1)	1	3	1/2	Tech Infra (W1)	1	3	2	Easy Access & Inclusion (O1)	1	2	3	Legal Constraints (T1)	1	3	4	2	5
Efficiency... (S2)	1/3	1	1/5	Costs & Energy (W2)	1/3	1	1/2	Economic Opps (O2)	1/2	1	2	Cybersecurity (T2)	1/3	1	2	1/2	3
Compliance & Reputation (S3)	2	5	1	Legal Uncertainties (W3)	1/2	2	1	Digitalization (O3)	1/3	1/2	1	Fluctuations (T3)	1/4	1/2	1	1/3	2
												Lack of Trust (T4)	1/2	2	3	1	4
												Greenwashing (T5)	1/5	1/3	1/2	1/4	1

According to the results presented in Table 4, when comparing the sub-factors within the strengths group, alignment with green banking practices and reputation enhancement are five times more important than the efficiency sub-factor. Similarly, within the weaknesses group, deficiencies in technical infrastructure were determined to be three times more important than high energy costs. In the comparison of the opportunities group’s sub-factors, easy market access and financial inclusion were found to be three times more important than digitalization. For the threat group, legal constraints were determined to be five times more important than the greenwashing sub-factor.

Table 5 presents the prioritized sub-factors derived from the SWOT-AHP analysis, incorporating expert evaluations from the green banking, blockchain, and carbon markets domains. The findings presented in the table provide both local and global priority weights, clearly demonstrating the relative importance of each sub-factor.

According to the global priorities, “Easy Market Access & Financial Inclusion, Attractiveness to Investors” (0.2430) emerges as a strategic opportunity in blockchain-based voluntary carbon markets. In second place is the sub-factor “Transparency, Traceability, and Reliability” (0.1824). Other significant priorities include “Economic Opportunities” (0.1395) and “Efficiency Improvement, Faster Transaction Speeds, and Reduced Costs” (0.0928).

Sub-factors such as “Greenwashing” (0.0065) and “Financial and Economic Fluctuations” (0.0143) are assigned the lowest global priorities, which indicates that while these threats do exist, they are perceived as having a relatively smaller impact on shaping strategic actions compared to the dominant opportunities and strengths.

Table 5. SWOT-AHP Strategic Prioritization of Sub-Factors

Factor	SWOT Group	Group Weight	Local Weight	Global Priority
Transparency...	Strengths	0.32	0.57	0.1824
Efficiency...	Strengths	0.32	0.29	0.0928
Compliance & Reputation	Strengths	0.32	0.14	0.0448
Tech Infra	Weaknesses	0.10	0.58	0.0580
Costs & Energy	Weaknesses	0.10	0.19	0.0190
Legal Uncertainties	Weaknesses	0.10	0.23	0.0230
Easy Access & Inclusion	Opportunities	0.45	0.54	0.2430
Economic Opps	Opportunities	0.45	0.31	0.1395
Digitalization	Opportunities	0.45	0.15	0.0675
Legal Constraints	Threats	0.13	0.46	0.0598
Cybersecurity	Threats	0.13	0.22	0.0286
Fluctuations	Threats	0.13	0.11	0.0143
Lack of Trust	Threats	0.13	0.16	0.0208
Greenwashing	Threats	0.13	0.05	0.0065

Overall, the distribution of weights demonstrates a clear emphasis on leveraging external opportunities and reinforcing internal strengths, while addressing weaknesses and threats with proportionately lower strategic focus. Moreover, the alignment between local and global priorities indicates that the pairwise comparison process was logically consistent, supporting the methodological robustness of the SWOT-AHP integration.

Figure 1 shows the global priority values for the 14 sub-factors of SWOT. In the figure, the closer the factors are to the extreme points, the higher their strategic priorities.

Figure 2. SWOT-AHP Strategic Prioritization Radar Chart*

* Green: Strengths, Red: Weaknesses, Blue: Opportunities, Orange: Threats.

O1 (Easy Access & Inclusion) is the sub-factor with the highest global priority (0.2430). This shows the strategic importance of external opportunities. S1 (Transparency, Traceability, and Reliability) is in second place (0.1824). This emphasizes that the transparency and traceability advantages of the system come to the fore. It is seen that the factors in the Opportunities main SWOT group are in a wide area. According to this result, it is understood that external opportunities are the most decisive element in strategic decisions. The sub-factors in the Threats group are seen to be more inward-looking. This result shows that the strategic impact of the threat factors is more limited. Weaknesses (W1–W3) factors are determined to have lower priority weights. On the other hand, some sub-factors such as W1 (Tech Infra) are seen to have a significant impact.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The integration of green banking practices with blockchain-based carbon credit systems represents a significant milestone in the digitalization of sustainable finance. However, this transformative process is shaped not only by technological innovations but also by multi-layered risks and challenges spanning legal, institutional, social, and economic dimensions. In this context, systematically addressing the weaknesses and threats identified through SWOT analysis is critical for constructing a resilient and sustainable digital financial architecture.

Firstly, existing regulatory gaps and legal uncertainties hinder the institutionalization and widespread acceptance of blockchain-based carbon credit systems within financial markets. Establishing clear and binding legal frameworks at the national level is essential to enhancing the system's predictability and investment security. In particular, explicitly defining the legal validity of smart contracts will ensure the safeguarding of digital transactions between parties. For organizations engaged in international carbon trading, developing standards based on mutual recognition principles for regulatory compliance and data sharing is recommended.

Inequalities in market access lead to the exclusion of SMEs and micro-scale projects from financial systems. Therefore, it is critical to develop blockchain-based micro carbon credit and green microfinance products to promote financial inclusion. Access to carbon markets for individuals and small businesses in developing countries can be facilitated by using tools such as mobile-based carbon wallets and carbon investment applications. In addition, open platforms developed under the leadership of public banks can support this process.

Concerns about ensuring data privacy and cybersecurity threats are elements that are specific to the nature of blockchain technology and will directly create a risk to public trust. In this context, cybersecurity standards need to be improved according to blockchain-based technological infrastructures to be integrated into carbon markets. Mandatory independent audit reports can be created to ensure security in smart contracts. In addition, full compliance with international data privacy regulations must be ensured. This obligation is important both to increase public trust and to fulfill legal obligations.

There is a lack of awareness and trust in this new technology on a societal level. This situation prevents the adoption and widespread use of such new technology-based applications. In this context, initiatives that will increase awareness in society, digital tools such as mobile applications and digital wallets that will contribute to people's ability to manage their carbon footprints can be introduced. In addition, applications such as "carbon transparency badges" can be encouraged by cooperating with civil society organizations and the media.

Investors' hesitations against the use of these technologies and liquidity shortages in the market also pose a threat to the financing of carbon projects. In this context, tax exemptions and subsidies that will be applied to institutions investing in such projects are important. In addition, transparent environmental impact reporting should be made mandatory. Establishing exchanges where carbon tokens can be bought and sold can also increase liquidity in the market. It can also pave the way for individual and institutional investors to enter the system. The policy recommendations mentioned are addressed with a holistic approach, considering both the financial and technical challenges and the legitimacy, inclusiveness and sustainability of the system. A system that integrates green banking practices with blockchain-based technologies will create a transparent, equitable and ethical framework in both climate finance and the age of digitalization. Concerns about ensuring data privacy and cybersecurity threats are elements that are specific to the nature of blockchain technology and will directly create a risk to public trust. In this context, cybersecurity standards need to be improved according to blockchain-based technological infrastructures to be integrated into carbon markets. Mandatory independent audit reports can be created to ensure security in smart contracts. In addition, full compliance with international data privacy regulations must be ensured. This obligation is important both to increase public trust and to fulfill legal obligations.

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